

EXPLORATION OF NEW APPLICATION OF MMCs MANUFACTURED BY SQUEEZE CASTING PROCESS

Hideharu Fukunaga

Department of Mechanical Engineering,
Hiroshima University,
Higashi-Hiroshima, 724, Japan

ABSTRACT

This contribution deals with the limitation and the acceleration to wide application of MMCs. The stress is laid on the newly developed reaction squeeze casting process. For the future application, the minute study on the commercialized MMCs teach us to utilize more than two MMC's characteristics of excellence by optimizing design. The reaction squeeze casting which makes the aluminum matrix tolerable for high temperature and severe wear, is offering the new MMC for the machine component manufactured by squeeze casting process.

Keywords: MMC, application, squeeze casting, reaction, TiO_2 , intermetallic compounds, Titanium aluminide.

1. INTRODUCTION

The ceramic fiber reinforced metal matrix composites (hereinafter, referred to MMC) have considerable potential for providing light weight components exhibiting high specific strength, high specific stiffness, excellent wear resistance, low thermal expansion and improved high temperature properties compared to the conventional materials. The attitude of the MMCs is offering a new approach to designer to achieve high performance and light weight of aircraft, motor vehicles, industrial machines and so on. However, the practical application for commercial use is not so widespread. The reason have to be seeked and the issues have to be solved. To advance the application of MMCs forward, the new composites are necessary for the high temperature use.

2. PROBLEMS TO WIDE APPLICATION OF MMC

The boron fiber reinforced aluminum composites (hereinafter, referred to B/Al) was applied for the development of aerospace[1] and military use, however, seldom used practically for civilian use because it is too expensive. The MMCs such as CF/Al, SiC_{pcs}/Al, Al₂O₃/Al, SiC_w/Al and so on, have been widely shown superior mechanical properties comparing to the conventional materials, but the practical usage for industry is not so many, they say, due to high costs and limited develop-

ment of appropriate fabrication technology. Indeed, the cost of the MMCs is one of the most important factors for applications, in which the decision making sequence could be used as shown in Fig. 1, but, there are still many problems to be solved so

Fig.1 Practical application sequence of MMC products.

that the MMCs come to be widely used as structural and functional materials for industry. The problems are given in the following:

1. Uncertainty of integrated total cost estimation.
2. Insufficiency in design data of reliability, fatigue strength, fracture toughness and resistance to heat cycle, etc.
3. Undevelopment in the design technology for anisotropic materials with low fracture strain and toughness.
4. Method of quality assurance.
5. Difficulty in secondary processing(rolling, forging, cutting, joining, and so on).

A little explanation and tackling the problems are given here. The first one as well as the second one is the problem always accompanying with the new materials along the history of the practical application, which have a new function and unknown cost. Although it is a necessary and perpetual subject to improve the productivity and economy of the MMCs, the most important problem is to establish the method which evaluate whether the cost is saving or not through the design and manufacture processes as well as the service life of the machines as shown in Fig1. It is required to evaluate accurately the effect of the light weight and the miniaturization by the use of the MMCs on the servicing performance, to solve the trade-off problems on the present technical level, and to make the decision of the practical application easier.

The second and third one are concerned with the essence of the composite concepts consisting of the ceramic fibers and the matrixes of Al alloys. Not only sufficient

strength data of the MMCs manufactured on the state of the art must be supplied to the designers, but also the improving strength data associated with the higher manufacturing technique should be delivered timely. However, the more important subject here is not the data supplies, but the factor finding to inherit MMC's characteristics from the view point of material sciences. For example, if the scattering factors of the strength were known, the manufacturer could shoot to make the MMCs with less scatter of strength. If the intrinsic low breaking strain and breaking toughness become clear, the matched designs could be considered. It is when designers can use MMCs confidently that the material behaviors of the MMCs have been analyzed. On the other hand, the design methodology based on the fracture strain criteria have to be developed, since it is impossible to improve the fracture strain remarkably as far as the ceramic fibers are used. Furthermore, because the continuous fiber reinforced MMCs are anisotropic composites, the design techniques should be developed to aid the optimum design using of the anisotropy positively. Thus MMC's properties can be tailored to satisfy certain design requirements, so it is necessary that they are manufactured as the products inherited the shape and size instantaneously. The MMCs are difficult-to-machine materials due to containing hard, breakable fibers. There are a great deal of tool wear in cutting. The extruding and rolling is available for the short fiber system, but is not applicable to the continuous fiber system. For continuous fiber system, the orientation designs are most suitable so that the fiber should not be cut off. As stated above, it could be said that the design techniques are the key technologies in future to proceed application of MMCs.

On the other hand, the inspection techniques, such as AE technique, X-ray technique, is not sufficient to detect the manufacturing defect and breaking fiber of MMCs. The commercialized products utilized the excellence of the wear resistance and the low expansion of MMCs has been realized already, however there is a delay yet in the practical application utilizing the specific strength of MMCs due to the lack of their reliability and quality assurance. There may be danger in the strength assurance after once overload is applied to MMC component because the local breaking of the ceramic fibers will occur[6]. So the accurate inspection technique should be established for strength assurance.

3. PRACTICAL APPLICATIONS OF MMCs

Recently the MMCs have been applied practically as the commercialized products in Japan as listed in Table 1 by overcoming the some problems as mentioned above[7]. Looking at these MMCs products one by one[8], the concepts to make use of each characteristic of the MMCs can be found, and it is remarkable to bring out the properties that the conventional materials could not compete with. The instances of these applied products teach us to make use of more than two kinds of superior characteristics of MMC at the commercialized product, such as specific strength and wear resistance, specific strength at high temperature and low heat expansion. The practical application is fulfilled when the best design has been carried out to satisfy the important requirements for components. The leadership should be transferred to the users from the material makers to decide properly the target component and to design it by user side.

It is characterized that most of the commercial products of MMC in Japan were fabricated by squeeze casting process, because of its high productivity and near net-shape formability, resulting to the low cost.

Table 1. Practical application of MMC for commercial products in Japan

Product	MMC system	Method of manufacture	Characteristics of applied MMC	Year (maker)
Vane, pressure side plate of oil pressure vane pump	Al ₂ O ₃ · SiO ₂ /AC4C	Squeeze casting(S.C.)	Wear resistance, noise damping	1987 (Hiroshima Aluminum)
Ring groove reinforced piston	Al ₂ O ₃ /Al-alloy	"	Light weight, wear resistance at high temperature	1983 (Toyota)
Golf goods Face of screwdriver	SiCpcs/ Al-alloy	"	Light weight, abrasion resistance	1984 (Nippon Carbon)
Connecting rod of gasoline engine	SUS fiber/ Al-alloy	"	Specific strength	1985 (Honda)
M6~8 bolt	SiCw/6061	S.C. Extrusion Tread rolling	Neutron absorption high temperature strength, little degasing	1986 (Toshiba)
Joint of aerospace structure	SiCw/7075	S.C. Rolling	Specific strength, low thermal expansion	1988 (Mitubishi)
Rotary compressor vane	SiCw/Al-17%Si-4%Cu alloy	S.C.	Specific strength, wear resistance, low thermal expansion	1989 (Sanyo)
Shock absorber cylinder	SiCp / Al-alloy	Compo-casting S.C. Extrusion	Light weight, wear resistance, thermal diffusivity	1989 (Mitubishi Aluminum)
Bicycle frame	SiCw/6061	Powder metallurgy HIP, Extrusion	Light weight, high specific rigidity	1989 (Kobe steel)
Diesel engine piston	SiCw / Al-alloy	S.C.	Light weight, wear resistance	1989 (Niigata)
Cylinder liner	Al ₂ O ₃ ,CF/ Al-alloy	Low pressure S.C.	Wear resistance, light weight	1991 (Honda)

4. NEW APPROACH OF SQUEEZE CASTING

The MMC endurable to the service at the high temperature are recently requested for the high efficiency gas turbine and the super sonic transportation in future. Figure 2 shows the maximum specific strength of various MMCs with increase in temperature, which has been reported before. The aluminum alloy matrix composites do not satisfy the requirement of high temperature use more than 300°C. The trend for high temperature composites causes the use of intermetallics-distributed or intermetallics matrix.

4.1 Squeeze casting of refractory matrix composites

Although the intermetallic compounds are difficult to melt, they have been employed to fabricate the high performance composites at high temperatures by squeeze casting.

Sakamoto[9] conditioned the molten FeAl at 1600°C in inert atmosphere, then pored and pressurized the melt on the δ -Al₂O₃ fiber preform at the temperature of 1100 °C with volume fraction of 10 to 30% under the final squeeze pressure of 30 MPa. The composites are sound and of the uniform distribution of fibers in the matrix, with the compressive strength of 700 to 2000 MPa.

Nourbakhsh[10-12] fabricated the continuous Al₂O₃(Fiber FP) fiber and α -Al₂O₃+20%ZrO₂(PRD-166) fiber reinforced Ti alloy(Ti-48Al-1Mn) and inter-metallic compounds (TiAl, Fe₃Al, Ni₃Al etc) composite by squeeze casting process. The process conditions are, 60% for volume fraction of fibers with 1600°C of

Fig.2 The maximum specific strength of various metal matrix composites, plotted by H.Fukunaga, which has been reported before.

preheating temperature, 1700°C for melt temperature of Ti alloy matrix with the final squeeze pressure of 1.5 to 2.8 MPa. One of the composites tested at room temperature were significantly weaker than the unreinforced alloy. However, when the strength was normalized with respect to density, no significant difference was found between the yield strength of the unreinforced matrix and the fracture strength of the composites tested at 1000°C.

These works demonstrate the great potentials for providing the light weight and complicated shape-component of machine for high temperature use.

4.2 Reaction squeeze casting

The conventional squeeze casting process has been successfully applied to the production of MMCs as one of the most effective manufacturing process of machine part. For a decade, a great interest has been taken in how the reaction could be avoided between the matrix and the reinforcement. In the contrary way to the conventional one, the reactions were positively promoted to produce new MMCs by the author. This method is called reaction squeeze casting[13]. The outline of the process is illustrated in Fig.3. The oxide powder, such as TiO₂ and NiO, and the metal powder such as Ni, Fe and Cu are embedded in the fiber preform. The conventional squeeze casting process is applied on the preform, then the reaction is taken place at the melt front, for example as following equations, resulting to produce intermetallic compounds.

Fig.3 Schematic presentation of reaction squeeze casting process to make the intermetallics in the matrix for high performance MMC.

The reaction products of Al_2O_3 and NiAl_3 are effective for improving the matrix strength at elevated temperatures and the wear resistance of MMC. Figure4 shows the high temperature strength of the new MMC, comparing to a conventional one, which is fabricated by reaction squeeze casting employing the preform of 20%

$\text{SiC}_w+5\% \text{TiO}_2+5\% \text{Ni}$ (Vf%) and molten pure aluminum. The new composites keeps still 320 MPa of bending strength at 400°C while the conventional one bears just 90 MPa. The X-ray diffraction identified Al_2O_3 , TiAl_3 , Ti_3Al and NiAl in the new composites, so they seems to strengthen the matrix by dispersing finely in the matrix.

The procedure itself is very simple and also it is convenient not to be necessary for changing the facilities of preforming, melting and casting. The reactive process, however, is rather complicated[14], so it is difficult to find out the optimum fabricating conditions and to control the structures. For an typical example, Fig.5 shows the hardness depending on the infiltrated distance, of which the composites was fabricated by reaction squeeze casting of the rutile type of 30% TiO_2 and molten aluminum[15]. The distance dependency of hardness comes from the temperature rise due to exothermic reaction and the Ti rich of concentration with the infiltrating length. This may be an issue for reaction squeeze casting in future. The solution heat treatment plays the remarkable role of homonizing the hardness, and also of controlling the hardness of composites ranging Hv130 to Hv500. Therefore, the process is now offering the another selection of materials suitable for the machine component serving under high temperature and severe wear circumference.

Fig.4 Comparison of bending strength of the composites at elevated temperatures between reaction squeeze cast and conventional squeeze cast.

The experimental report increases in number in which deals with the fabrication of MMC by utilizing the reaction between the solid reinforcement and the molten metal or the atmosphere and the molten metal. Suganuma[16], Nishida[17] and Horsfall[18] carried out successfully the reaction squeeze casting by employing the couple of 5%Ni powder+Al₂O₃·SiO₂ short fiber/molten Al alloy, 50%Ti fiber/molten pure aluminum, and Ti powder+Al₂O₃ short fiber/molten aluminum,

Fig.5 Hardness of the composites by reaction squeeze casting.

respectively. The results were successful to fabricate the Nickel-, Titanium-aluminide matrix composites. As for the process utilized the reaction between the atmosphere and the molten metal, PRIMEX and DIMOX process have been proposed. They are especially noticed as pressureless process.

5. SUMMARY

The problems on the practical applications of MMCs by squeeze casting process have been presented. The newly developed reaction squeeze casting process is

introduced. This is an effort to promote the widespread use of MMCs for industry with the aid of gathering the wisdom of the researchers and engineers concerning the MMC's science and technology.

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